

Healthy Workplace and Employees' Wellness: Promoting Wellbeing and Productivity at Work in the New Normal

Maria Roxane B. Parica¹, Dr. Edilberto Z. Andal², Dr. Eden C. Callo³,
Dr. Darwin D. Ofrin⁴, Dr. Paulina Q. Quisido⁵

¹Faculty of Laguna State Polytechnic University - San Pablo City Campus, Philippines

²Dean at Laguna State Polytechnic University - San Pablo City Campus, Philippines

³Vice President of Academic Affairs of Laguna State Polytechnic University - San Pablo City Campus, Philippines

⁴Dean at Laguna State Polytechnic University - San Pablo City Campus, Philippines

⁵Faculty of Laguna State Polytechnic University - San Pablo City Campus, Philippines

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8081376>

Published Date: 26-June-2023

Abstract: This study focused on the healthy workplace and employees' wellness dimensions in the promotion of wellbeing and productivity at work in the new normal of the non-teaching employees of Laguna State Polytechnic University San Pablo City Campus. The study used descriptive method with an aid of spearman rho that identified significant relationships between healthy workplace towards employees' wellbeing and productivity at work in the new normal and employees' wellness dimensions towards wellbeing and productivity at work in the new normal. As to result, the respondents highly observed a healthy workplace, highly practiced the employees' wellness, highly experienced the employees' wellbeing at work, and highly experienced the employees' productivity at work in the new normal. Therefore, it rejects the null hypothesis of the study. Hence, to support the university practices, the study proposes an improvement on the healthy workplace and employees' wellness to promote wellbeing and productivity at work in the new normal and highly recommends an extension project entitled "Project Wellness".

Keywords: Employees' wellbeing, employees' wellness, healthy workplace, new normal and productivity at work.

I. INTRODUCTION

A place where everyone works in collaboration to achieve an agreed vision for the health and well-being of all the workers is a healthy workplace according to the World Health Organization (WHO). Its concept centers on workplace facilities, work organization, workplace culture, and health resources that can protect and promote the health of an employee which pertains to wellness (Stoewen, 2016). However, wellness is an initiative from an individual as an active pursuit of activities, lifestyles, intentions, choices and actions towards a state of holistic health. Combining healthy workplace and employees' wellness leads to an optimal state of health and wellbeing.

Amidst the pandemic, the workplace that was previously considered safe are now viewed as potentially hazardous and has become a common source of transmission of COVID-19 (Sinclair, Probst, Watson, & Bazzoli, 2021). Therefore a lot of alterations at work have been enforced. Thus, the virus caused changes not only in the workplace but also in the wellness of an individual which may relatively affect an organization. Academic institutions in the Philippines who continued providing services in the new normal followed the Civil Service Commission announcement on Alternative Work Arrangement such as work from home and skeletal workforce set-up. Faculties shifted to online teaching-and-learning modalities while the essential workers continued school operations following protocols. The impact of the pandemic to the essential workers was unprecedented, where it demands employees to adapt quickly to the new procedures and protocol

with heightened job necessities which lead to increased levels of stress with unrealistic time pressures (Hafner, Stolk, & Saunders, 2015). The abrupt changes prompted different perspectives on lifestyle, health, economies, workplace, and productivity (Ahorsu & Lin, 2020, Asio, 2021, and Sinclair, Probst, Watson, & Bazzoli, 2020). Hence, essential employees experienced extreme transformation in their standards and operating procedures (Kumar, 2021). This adjustment in the workplace and lifestyle of an individual was called the new normal. Although, countless measures were implemented to ensure employees' wellness, Sabando & Alo (2021) revealed that the overall health and health promotion in the Philippines lag behind other countries. Nonetheless, most studies focused on the health status of college students and not the employees (Kpoe & Laborde, 2020).

Consequently, there is a connection in employees' well-being and productivity at work that is influenced by the resources and working environment in an organization, as well as each person's initiative to promote their own wellness especially during times of environmental change. That is why this study would like to focus on the essential employees of Laguna State Polytechnic University who continued to work on-site in the new normal. Hence, with the changes during the so called new normal including the changes in the workplace, in the lifestyle of the employees and the changes in the environment, may affect both an individual and its organization. Therefore, understanding a healthy workplace and employees' wellness may be essential to develop interventions in promoting wellbeing and productivity at work.

II. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Perception of the Employees on the Healthy Workplace in the New Normal

Table 1. Level of Physical Work Environment

Statements	Mean	SD	VI
1. Is always safe, and secure and free from any hazardous chemical.	3.65	0.48	HO
2. has good working facilities such as offices, workstations with all the materials, equipment and devices needed to perform my duties and responsibilities completely.	3.73	0.47	HO
3. ensures good housekeeping by maintaining the cleanliness in the worksite with routinized disinfection to stop the spread of the virus	3.52	0.56	HO
4. abides with the IATF protocols to prevent the transmission of diseases like checking of temperature and wearing of mask.	3.58	0.52	HO
5. installed physical barriers, rope, or markers on the worksite to promote physical distancing among the employees and the clients.	3.64	0.48	HO
Overall	3.62	0.35	HO

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Highly Observed), 2.50-3.49 (Observed), 1.50-2.49 (Slightly Observed), 1.00-1.49 (Not Observed)

In the new normal, the respondents categorized their workplace as safe, secure, and free from any viruses shown in table 1. It can be described as comfortable and conducive, thus, it is very important that the university provides a healthy physical work environment to prevent the transmission of the virus because the workplace, which was formerly regarded as reasonably safe, is now a common place of viral transmission (Sinclair, Probst, Watson, & Bazzoli, 2021).

Table 2. Level of Psychosocial Work Environment

Statements	Mean	SD	VI
1. gives me enough time to complete my tasks.	3.58	0.52	HO
2. treats all employee equally regardless of their position.	3.46	0.57	O
3. permits flexibility to deal with work-life conflict situations especially with regards to health and safety.	3.59	0.49	HO
4. does not tolerate harassment, bullying and discrimination in the workplace.	3.65	0.55	HO
5. abide to all legal standards and laws regarding workplace conditions and policies to supplement the laws like maternity leave and alike.	3.66	0.50	HO
Overall	3.59	0.42	HO

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Highly Observed), 2.50-3.49 (Observed), 1.50-2.49 (Slightly Observed), 1.00-1.49 (Not Observed)

Table 2 exposes that the employees do not totally experience equal treatment in the institution. There are different factors that may have affected the result of this indicator like the position or the terms of contract in an organization especially that respondents of this study are a combination of regular, casual, and job order service workers who have different arrangements in the workplace. It reveals the need to further study the equality in the workplace. Correspondingly, treating employees with fairness and respect is essential for a positive and productive work environment. When employees feel valued and respected, they are more motivated, and committed to work. It is supported by Rosales (2015) which states that positive work relationship is a source of enrichment, meaning, and learning that help individuals and the organizations progress.

Table 3. Level of Personal Health Resources

Statements	Mean	SD	VI
1. has medical facilities with medical personnel who assists employees who needs medical assistance.	3.58	0.60	HO
2. has fitness facilities that is functioning well and accessible employees to be physically fit.	3.51	0.57	HO
3. encourages physical activity through promotional campaigns like fitness programs, competitions, and other recreational activities.	3.48	0.61	O
4. arrange seminars to promote awareness and educate workers on stress management techniques and training to maintain health and safety during crisis such as earthquake and fire drill.	3.52	0.54	HO
5. provide assistance and initiates COVID-19 vaccination.	3.57	0.52	HO
Overall	3.53	0.43	HO

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Highly Observed), 2.50-3.49 (Observed), 1.50-2.49 (Slightly Observed), 1.00-1.49 (Not Observed)

The university provides health services to its employees as presented on table 3, although, it lacks promotion. There is a need to review the wellness programs of the university. It is supported by Pilgrim & Bohnet-Joschko (2019) which states that to sustain health promotion is to identify existing means. Also, it should not be limited to physical activity (Basińska-Zych & Springer, 2021). Moreover, to encourage participation, it should consider the needs of the employees. Evidence reveals that employee health promotion can be successful if employees actually take part in it (Lier, Breuer, & Dallmeyer, 2019).

2.1 Perception of the Employees on Wellness in the New Normal

Table 4. Level of Physical Dimension of Wellness

Statements	Mean	SD	VI
1. eat nutritious food and drink at least eight (8) glasses of water daily.	3.29	0.60	P
2. get enough sleep and feel energized throughout the day.	3.16	0.57	P
3. perform physical activity such as walking at least 30 minutes a day to maintain my wellness.	3.20	0.76	P
4. rest, drink medication and/or seek medical assistance when needed.	3.41	0.63	P
5. comply with health protocol like wearing of face mask, regular hand washing and covering my mouth when coughing to protect myself and others from getting ill.	3.64	0.50	HP
Overall	3.34	0.44	P

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Highly Practiced), 2.50-3.49 (Practiced), 1.50-2.49 (Slightly Practiced), 1.00-1.49 (Not Practiced)

Table 4 shows that employees adhere to guidelines protecting themselves from the virus, though, it also reveals that some do not practice regular 8 – hour sleep, thus, leads to reduced energy and affects the performance of an individual and his quality of life. It is supported by Pilcher & Morris (2020) who states that sleep impacts work performance.

Table 5. Level of Intellectual Dimension of Wellness

Statements	Mean	SD	VI
1. perform my duties and responsibilities with knowledge and competency.	3.68	0.47	HP
2. make important decisions on my own and conceptualize solutions to my problems.	3.58	0.50	HP
3. critically consider the opinions and information presented by others and provide constructive feedback.	3.63	0.48	HP
4. seek personal growth by learning new skills.	3.63	0.54	HP
5. look for ways to use my creativity and critical thinking skills.	3.60	0.51	HP
Overall	3.62	0.41	HP

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Highly Practiced), 2.50-3.49 (Practiced), 1.50-2.49 (Slightly Practiced), 1.00-1.49 (Not Practiced)

In table 5, respondents recognize their own intellectual wellness as they respect other's opinion and engage in creative and exciting mental activities. Thus, engages in activities that develop his capability to think logically and rationally to broaden personal growth and learn new skills. Thus, people who are intellectually strong are committed to lifelong learning through the continuous acquisition of skills and knowledge (Strout, Fayeza Ahmed, Howard, Sassatelli, & Mcfadden, 2018).

Table 6. Level of Social Dimension of Wellness

Statements	Mean	SD	VI
1. actively participate and contribute to a group or community where I belong.	3.57	0.50	HP
2. appreciate the love, respect and support coming from my family and friends especially whenever I needed help.	3.79	0.41	HP
3. am comfortable in meeting and socializing with new people.	3.60	0.58	HP
4. respect my individuals as a person regardless of their status or position.	3.72	0.47	HP
5. maintain healthy relationships with my friends and loved ones through constant communication despite the lockdown and social distancing.	3.72	0.45	HP
Overall	3.68	0.40	HP

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Highly Practiced), 2.50-3.49 (Practiced), 1.50-2.49 (Slightly Practiced), 1.00-1.49 (Not Practiced)

Table 6 presents that employees are comfortable in socializing with new people, they respect individuals as a person and maintains healthy social relationship despite the new normal. It reveals that they can effectively interact with people and have a support system, therefore, they have a healthy social relationship. Strout, Fayeza Ahmed, Howard, Sassatelli, & Mcfadden (2018) agreed that social wellness is the ability of an individual to form and maintain positive social relationships.

Table 7. Level of Emotional Dimension of Wellness

Statements	Mean	SD	VI
1. feel comfortable in expressing my emotions.	3.39	0.67	P
2. can easily recognize and manage my stressors.	3.55	0.55	HP
3. confidently perform my duties and responsibilities at home and at work.	3.71	0.46	HP
4. accept the feedback and constructive criticism I received with positive attitude thinking I can use it to promote my own wellness.	3.65	0.54	HP
5. control my emotions especially when there are things I cannot control.	3.61	0.49	HP
Overall	3.58	0.42	HP

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Highly Practiced), 2.50-3.49 (Practiced), 1.50-2.49 (Slightly Practiced), 1.00-1.49 (Not Practiced)

Table 7 reveals that employees believe in themselves that they can do the task they needed to perform because they are confident in their ability with a "can-do" attitude. However, the results also exhibits that they are skeptical in sharing their emotions. People communicate their emotions mostly with the expectation of promoting emotional recovery. It benefits mental health through a variety of indirect effects, including reinforcement of social relationships, affection and warmth. Moreover, Peña-Sarrionandia, Mikolajczak, & Gross (2015) described emotion sharing and its effects to mental health such as the construction or reinforcement of social bonds and the transference of affection and warmth.

Table 8. Level of Occupational Dimension of Wellness

Statements	Mean	SD	VI
1. am happy and satisfied with my job.	3.47	0.56	<i>P</i>
2. perform my duties and responsibilities with competency.	3.67	0.47	<i>HP</i>
3. share my knowledge, talents and abilities that leads to improved output at work.	3.68	0.47	<i>HP</i>
4. look for ways to improve my performance at work like enhancing my knowledge and trying out different strategies.	3.65	0.50	<i>HP</i>
5. participate in the seminars and trainings for my professional growth.	3.61	0.51	<i>HP</i>
Overall	3.62	0.41	<i>HP</i>

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (*Highly Practiced*), 2.50-3.49 (*Practiced*), 1.50-2.49 (*Slightly Practiced*), 1.00-1.49 (*Not Practiced*)

In table 8, the data shows employees were frequently satisfied with their job. There are individuals who tend to work in a field different from their profession due to fear of unemployment, location, skills, and requirements. Also, others tend to explore careers that will benefit them. Ortega & Cruz (2016) supports this stating that out of fear of unemployment, applicants get a job different from what they have studied. Nonetheless, results affirm the occupational wellbeing of the employees with regards to competency, expanding knowledge, and pursuing professional development. Moreover, when employees perform their job with competency and continuously enhance their skills it contributes to the achievement of goal of the organization as verified by Rinne, Koskinen, Leino-Kilpi, Saaranen, & Salminen (2021) which states that maintaining occupational wellness is vital not only for the wellbeing of the individual, but also for the whole working community.

Table 9. Level of Spiritual Dimension of Wellness

Statements	Mean	SD	VI
1. live with purpose and meaning in life.	3.70	0.48	<i>HP</i>
2. act and speak freely in accordance with my personal values and beliefs.	3.58	0.51	<i>HP</i>
3. respect and keep an open mind about others' beliefs & values.	3.75	0.44	<i>HP</i>
4. engage in acts of caring and goodwill without expecting something in return.	3.68	0.49	<i>HP</i>
5. strives to grow spiritually through participating in activities such as religious gatherings.	3.56	0.57	<i>HP</i>
Overall	3.65	0.38	<i>HP</i>

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (*Highly Practiced*), 2.50-3.49 (*Practiced*), 1.50-2.49 (*Slightly Practiced*), 1.00-1.49 (*Not Practiced*)

The table 9 exhibits that employees are open-minded towards dissimilar religions, beliefs, and values. However, employees appear to be less engaged to spiritual progress, though, participating in spiritual activities enhances one's perspective in life as it is an avenue to discover hope, comfort and one's own purpose. It has an impact on someone's faith and dedication, which shapes self-fulfillment and may influence wellbeing and productivity. Moreover, several aspects including meaning, purpose, spiritual coping, compassion, and spiritual experiences, have been associated with better mental health (Kristeller & Jordan, 2018). Likewise, Strange, Troutman-Jordan, & Mixer (2023) states that spiritual engagement reduces worry and enhances sense of peace and positive outlook in life.

2.2 Perception of the Employees on Wellbeing at Work in the New Normal

Table 10. Level of Positive Emotion Wellbeing at Work

Statements	Mean	SD	VI
1. I look forward to going to work every day.	3.62	0.59	<i>HE</i>
2. I feel motivated in performing my duties and responsibilities at work.	3.68	0.54	<i>HE</i>
3. I am grateful for the reward and appreciation that I receive at work.	3.59	0.53	<i>HE</i>
4. I am comfortable and satisfied with my career growth in this university.	3.47	0.59	<i>E</i>
5. I am optimistic, and resilient especially towards unexpected changes at work.	3.63	0.54	<i>HE</i>
Overall	3.60	0.45	<i>HE</i>

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (*Highly Experienced*), 2.50-3.49 (*Experienced*), 1.50-2.49 (*Slightly Experienced*), 1.00-1.49 (*Not Experienced*)

Table 10 presents that employee enjoy what they do at work that is why they are motivated in performing their duties even in the new normal. Although, it appears that there are no opportunities for the employees to advance professionally at the university. Organizations that offer career development opportunities for employees foster a relationship of reciprocal investment that links career advancement to organizational commitment (Biswakarma, 2016).

Table 11. Level of Engagement Wellbeing at Work

Statements	Mean	SD	VI
1. I avoid interruptions and disturbances while performing my job.	3.40	0.56	E
2. I keep my focus on the schedule so that I may perform my entire task for the day.	3.59	0.51	HE
3. there are times that I lose track of time because I am eager to finish my job.	3.42	0.60	E
4. I am excited to learn new things that will promote my skills and expertise at work.	3.63	0.52	HE
5. I actively participate in the programs organized by the university for my own growth.	3.56	0.57	HE
Overall	3.52	0.44	HE

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Highly Experienced), 2.50-3.49 (Experienced), 1.50-2.49 (Slightly Experienced), 1.00-1.49 (Not Experienced)

In table 11 shows the desire of the employees to learn new things that would increase their abilities and competency. They are engaged even in tasks that are challenging and eager to learn new things. However, it also implies that they get distracted during working hours. Distractions or interruptions can be anything that diverts attention such as defective equipment, shortage of supplies, co-workers who needs help, and more that impedes or delays work. Thus, Keller, Meier, Elfering, & Semmer (2020) describes work interruptions as circumstances that impede or delay the achievement of a goal.

Table 12. Level of Relationship Wellbeing at Work

Statements	Mean	SD	VI
1. I trust the whole department I am at.	3.50	0.71	HE
2. I rely on my colleagues whenever I needed help/assistance.	3.60	0.53	HE
3. I feel respected, trusted, and valued at work.	3.57	0.55	HE
4. I do not have any conflict with my other colleagues.	3.54	0.64	HE
5. I never felt any unpleasant occurrences between me and your co-workers like bullying or threatening.	3.61	0.61	HE
Overall	3.56	0.46	HE

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Highly Experienced), 2.50-3.49 (Experienced), 1.50-2.49 (Slightly Experienced), 1.00-1.49 (Not Experienced)

It is presented in table 12 that employees feel safe and comfortable because there is a good social relationship in the workplace. Thus, relationship at work includes feelings of belonging and satisfaction with the social networks which is favorable to one's health. Moreover, Pandey, et al. (2021) confirmed that developing friendships or meaningful interactions with others has an impact on one's mental health, happiness, and physical health. However, it also reveals that not all employees have complete faith in every member of their team. Trust is a vital aspect in a relationship which starts from social interaction. Hence, when a person believes that his team is dependable and supportive leads in satisfaction at work and promotes wellbeing. According to Pravamayee (2014), maintaining positive work relationships will not only increase one's engagement and commitment to the organization, but also opens doors to crucial initiatives, career development, and raises.

Table 13. Level of Meaning Wellbeing at Work

Statements	Mean	SD	VI
1. I know the importance of my job.	3.79	0.41	HE
2. my role contributes to the overall output of the university.	3.70	0.48	HE
3. my work serves a purpose not only in the university but also in my life.	3.72	0.45	HE
4. I feel fulfilled when I put effort in performing my task at work.	3.75	0.43	HE
5. I am working to achieve my goals in life.	3.73	0.45	HE
Overall	3.74	0.40	HE

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Highly Experienced), 2.50-3.49 (Experienced), 1.50-2.49 (Slightly Experienced), 1.00-1.49 (Not Experienced)

Table 13 shows that employees are aware of the importance of their role in the institution and value their job, hence, giving them a sense of purpose at work. When a person is aware of their purpose, feels fulfilled, and is actively contributing to meaningful activities, they are more likely to recognize meaning in their lives (Lovett & Lovett, 2016). It also suggests that they need affirmation of their contribution in institution because they want to feel that their efforts help the institution achieve its goals (Cote, 2019). Thus, Sandler (2023) verified that people with purpose in life live longer, happier, and healthier.

Table 14. Level of Accomplishment Wellbeing at Work

Statements	Mean	SD	VI
1. I work hard to improve my performance every day.	3.70	0.46	HE
2. I set my own goals at work to help me achieve my task efficiently.	3.67	0.47	HE
3. I feel proud of myself whenever I accomplish my job.	3.71	0.46	HE
4. I feel great when my effort is recognized at work.	3.71	0.46	HE
5. I am challenged to enhance my skills for my own growth.	3.73	0.47	HE
Overall	3.70	0.39	HE

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Highly Experienced), 2.50-3.49 (Experienced), 1.50-2.49 (Slightly Experienced), 1.00-1.49 (Not Experienced)

Table 14 exhibits positive sense of accomplishment where employees feel proud of their achievements especially when their efforts are recognized. Thus, they continue to enhance their own skills for their own growth which entails personal ambition and passion in achieving mastery of a task. Studies verified that feeling accomplished can reinforced through demonstration of mastery of skills where people often value their own creation more than others (Farmer & Cotter, 2021).

2.3 Perception of the Employees on Productivity at Work in the New Normal

Table 15. Level of Productivity at Work as to Job Demand

Statements	Mean	SD	VI
1. I always comply with the required output even with immediate deadline.	3.59	0.71	HE
2. I use my skills, expertise, and even creativity to achieve our goal especially those tasks needing a rapid solution.	3.69	0.49	HE
3. I perform my duties professionally regardless of the changes in the environment.	3.74	0.44	HE
4. I complete task assigned by my supervisor even though it is beyond my capabilities.	3.70	0.46	HE
5. I accomplish my task even though I am not feeling well.	3.60	0.53	HE
Overall	3.66	0.42	HE

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Highly Experienced), 2.50-3.49 (Experienced), 1.50-2.49 (Slightly Experienced), 1.00-1.49 (Not Experienced)

In table 15, employees use their skills, knowledge, and talents to support the organization achieve its goals even when the assignment is beyond their capabilities. It confirms that they can comply with the challenging demand at work. Job demands may also be challenging to some extent. An example is a tight deadline also boost performance (Schaufeli, 2017).

Table 16. Level of Productivity at Work as to Job Control

Statements	Mean	SD	VI
1. I make sure that my task and responsibilities are on schedule.	3.61	0.51	HE
2. I decide which task should be done first and which can be done at a later time.	3.62	0.51	HE
3. I use my own style, strategy and able to apply my expertise and potential in doing my job.	3.68	0.49	HE
4. I share my ideas and participate in the decision making at work.	3.71	0.46	HE
5. I resolve issues/problems on my own arising during work.	3.57	0.53	HE
Overall	3.64	0.43	HE

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Highly Experienced), 2.50-3.49 (Experienced), 1.50-2.49 (Slightly Experienced), 1.00-1.49 (Not Experienced)

Table 16 confirm that employees has job control as comply with the schedule, decide which task to perform and use their own style and strategy in accomplishing their job. It therefore contributes to their determination to perform well. It is supported by Kossek, Valcour, & Lirio (2014) which promotes working smarter rather than working longer and intensely.

Table 17. Level of Productivity at Work

Statements	Mean	SD	VI
1. Job Demand	3.66	0.42	HE
2. Job Control	3.64	0.43	HE
Overall	3.65	0.43	HE

Legend: 3.50-4.00 (Highly Experienced), 2.50-3.49 (Experienced), 1.50-2.49 (Slightly Experienced), 1.00-1.49 (Not Experienced)

The table 17 displays the level of productivity of the respondents in terms of job demand and job control, where, it can be further expressed as very high. It entails the success of the organization however, it is challenging to balance job demand and job control. Isham, Mair, & Jackson, 2020 states that high demands and the high level of control posed a challenge to the employees. Studies also confirmed that control over work is beneficial in reducing workloads and complying with job demands (Kossek, Valcour, & Lirio, 2014, Portoghese, Galletta, Coppola, Finco, & Campagna, 2014 and Schaufeli, 2017).

2.4 Significant Relationship between the Healthy Workplace and the Employee’s Wellbeing in the New Normal

Table 18. Test of Relationship between Healthy Workplace and Employee’s Wellbeing

Healthy Workplace	Employee’s Wellbeing at Work				
	Positive Emotion	Engagement	Meaning	Relationship	Accomplishment
Physical Work Environment	.542**	.488**	.459**	.525**	.411**
Psychosocial Work Environment	.580**	.478**	.573**	.530**	.550**
Personal Health Resources	.392**	.284**	.426**	.387**	.368**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 18 reveals that healthy workplace has a strong association with employee’s wellbeing at work indicating that employees are optimistic, motivated, feels respected, and valued at work. It also shows that they are empowered to perform better as they achieve their goals. It reveals that the university treats individuals fairly, supports their needs, and offers benefits which encourage positive behaviors. Putri, Ekowati, Supriyanto, & Mukaffi (2019) states that employees perform well and feel comfortable if they have a favorable environment. It also reveals that the university is clean, safe, and secured so employees can stay focused, hence, can increase engagement as De-la-Calle-Durán & Rodríguez-Sánchez (2021) discussed that a workplace that supports engagement also supports employees' wellbeing and productivity.

2.5 Significant Relationship between the Healthy Workplace and the Employee’s Productivity in the New Normal

Table 19. Test of Relationship Between Healthy Workplace and Employee’s Productivity at Work

Healthy Workplace	Employee’s Productivity at Work	
	Job Demand	Job Control
Physical Work Environment	.557**	.475**
Psychosocial Work Environment	.452**	.528**
Personal Health Resources	.421**	.302**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 19 exhibits that job demand is affected by the work environment as employees perform their obligations even beyond their capabilities provided that all resources are available and working. Orji & Yakubu (2020) proved the link between the quantity and quality employee productivity and resources for accomplishing a set of goals. Hence, job demands should be compensated by the resources at work (Schaufeli, 2017). Likewise, psychological work environment affects job

control where employees have control over the goals. They can decide which task should be prioritized and perform their role with their own strategies applying their expertise and creativity. According to Isham, Mair, & Jackson (2020) job control was associated with all favorable outcomes such as greater levels of mental health, job performance, and job satisfaction.

2.6 Significant Relationship between the Employee’s Wellness and Employee’s Wellbeing at Work in the New Normal

Table 20. Test of Relationship Between Healthy Workplace and Employee’s Wellbeing

Employee’s Wellness	Employee’s Wellbeing at Work				
	Positive Emotion	Engagement	Meaning	Relationship	Accomplishment
Physical	.564**	.574**	.449**	.392**	.474**
Intellectual	.602**	.535**	.618**	.548**	.709**
Social	.687**	.545**	.594**	.637**	.666**
Emotional	.614**	.603**	.647**	.612**	.715**
Spiritual	.603**	.500**	.623**	.606**	.712**
Occupational	.737**	.632**	.657**	.641**	.632**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 20 shows that employee’s wellness is significantly correlated to employee’s wellbeing at work emphasizing occupational wellness’ strong positive relationship towards positive emotion, engagement, meaning and relationship. Evidence illustrates employees are happy and satisfied with their jobs as they look forward to go to work every day, they perform their tasks competently, and actively participate in training and seminars to further their growth. Additionally, it proved a positive working relationship in the university. Thus, workplace trust relationship enables cooperation among colleagues which serves as motivation (Okello & Gilson, 2015). Hence, employee’s wellness boosts employee’s wellbeing at work is corroborated by Scheepers, Boerebach, Arah, Heineman, & Lombarts (2015) which states that high levels of occupational wellbeing leads to dedication at work and improved wellbeing. On the other hand, the results show the connection of emotional wellness and his accomplishment. Even though employees are confident enough to accomplish their tasks, they still strive to enhance their skills and abilities every day because people seek accomplishment, competence, success, and mastery for their own satisfaction (Moog, 2021). People feel great and proud whenever they accomplish things especially when recognized, thus, it raises confidence and self-esteem (Kumar & Dwivedi, 2023). Altogether, it proves that wellbeing at work is mainly enhanced through individual’s initiative of promoting and maintaining one’s own wellness.

2.7 Significant Relationship between the Employee’s Wellness and Employee’s Productivity at Work in the New Normal

Table 21. Test of Relationship Between Employee’s Wellness and Employee’s Productivity at Work

Employee’s Wellness	Employee’s Productivity at Work	
	Job Demand	Job Control
Physical	.395**	.466**
Intellectual	.635**	.636**
Social	.497**	.666**
Emotional	.567**	.649**
Spiritual	.617**	.642**
Occupational	.487**	.556**

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed), * Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 21 reveals a significant correlation linking employee’s wellness and employee’s productivity at work exhibiting the relationship of intellectual wellness and job demand. It implies that employees perform their duties with knowledge and competency that is why they comply with the required output at work. Also, they can make important decisions and carry out their responsibilities professionally by utilizing their critical thinking abilities, expertise, and creativity. A competent employee can utilize his own knowledge, skills, and expertise to improve productivity which enables him to meet the

deadline (Osborne & Hammoud, 2017). While regarding social wellness and job control, employees share their ideas and engage in workplace decision-making which lead to increased output at work. Hence, job control at work refers to employees' ability to be creative, participate in decision-making, and affect how they carry out their tasks (Mazzetti, Biolcati, Guglielmi, Vallesi, & Schaufeli, 2016). It boosts both productivity and wellbeing because it was positively associated with all favorable outcomes such as job satisfaction, life satisfaction, and family satisfaction (Isham, Mair, & Jackson, 2020).

III. CONCLUSION

Overall, healthy workplace has a strong association employee's wellbeing at work with a clean, safe and secured facilities at work contributes on how engaged the employees in performing their job. Additionally, respondents are optimistic, motivated, and empowered in performing their duties because there is a good social relationship, fairness, and equality in the workplace. Also, results reveal a strong positive relation between healthy workplace and employee's productivity at work in the new normal. It shows that job demands should be compensated with resources in the workplace while application of one's own expertise and strategy in performing their job contributes to greater levels of performance. Employees' wellness also has a strong positive relationship with employees' wellbeing at work in the new normal. Positive emotion, engagement, meaning, and relationship are affected by the occupational wellness of an individual while accomplishment is influenced by their emotion. Thus, their motivation, competence, and their sense of purpose at work are at peak when they are satisfied. Moreover, employees are confident to accomplish their tasks, yet, they still strive to enhance their skills for their own satisfaction. Lastly, the study exhibits strong positive relationship between employee's wellness and employees' productivity at work in the new normal as respondents comply with the demands at work because they are competent and knowledgeable. Additionally, they can modify the completion of their tasks at work since they highly experience job control.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to express their sincerest appreciation to all those people behind the success of this study that inspires and motivate them to pursue this study.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ahorsu, D. K., & Lin, C.-Y. (2020). The Association Between Health Status And Insomnia, Mental Health, And Preventive Behaviors: The Mediating Role Of Fear Of COVID-19. *Gerontology And Geriatric Medicine*.
- [2] Asio, J. M. (2021). Determinants Of Work Productivity Among Selected Tertiary Education Employees: A Precovid-19 Pandemic Analysis. *International Journal Of Didactical Studies*, 8 Pages.
- [3] Basińska-Zych, A., & Springer, A. (2021). Organizational And Individual Outcomes Of Health Promotion Strategies—A Review Of Empirical Research. *International Journal Of Environmental Research And Public Health*.
- [4] Biswakarma, G. (2016). Organizational Career Growth And Employees' Turnover Intentions: An Empirical Evidence From Nepalese Private Commercial Banks. *International Academic Journal Of Organizational Behavior And Human Resource Management*.
- [5] Cote, R. (2019). Motivating Multigenerational Employees: Is There A Difference? . *Journal Of Leadership, Accountability And Ethics*.
- [6] De-La-Calle-Durán, M.-C., & Rodríguez-Sánchez, J.-L. (2021). Employee Engagement And Wellbeing In Times Of COVID-19: A Proposal Of The 5Cs Model. *International Journal Of Environmental Research And Public Health*.
- [7] Farmer, N., & Cotter, E. W. (2021). Well-Being And Cooking Behavior: Using The Positive Emotion, Engagement, Relationships, Meaning, And Accomplishment (PERMA) Model As A Theoretical Framework. *Frontiers In Psychology*.
- [8] Hafner, M., Stolk, C. V., & Saunders, C. (2015). Health, Wellbeing And Productivity In The Workplace. A Britain's Healthiest Company Summary Report. Santa Monica, Calif., And Cambridge, UK: RAND Corporation Report.
- [9] Isham, A., Mair, S., & Jackson, T. (2020). Wellbeing And Productivity: A Review Of The Literature. Centre For The Understanding Of Sustainable Prosperity.

- [10] Keller, A. C., Meier, L. L., Elfering, A., & Semmer, N. K. (2020). Please Wait Until I Am Done! Longitudinal Effects Of Work Interruptions On Employee Well-Being. *Work & Stress*.
- [11] Kossek, E. E., Valcour, M., & Lirio, P. (2014). Organizational Strategies For Promoting Work–Life Balance And Wellbeing. *Work And Wellbeing*.
- [12] Kpoeh, H. E., & Laborde, C. C. (2020). Health Profile Of Faculty And Staff At The Adventist University Of The Philippines: A Basis For Workplace Health Promotion. *East African Journal Of Education And Social Sciences (EAJESS)*.
- [13] Kristeller, J. L., & Jordan, K. D. (2018). Mindful Eating: Connecting With The Wise Self, The Spiritual Self. *Frontiers In Psychology*.
- [14] Kumar, P. (2021). V-5 Model Of Employee Engagement. *Vision*.
- [15] Kumar, A., & Dwivedi, P. R. (2023). To Explore The Role Of PERMA-Model Of Wellbeing In Job Hunt Of Management Students In Delhi-NCR Region. *International Journal Of Scientific Development And Research (IJSDR)*.
- [16] Lier, L. M., Breuer, C., & Dallmeyer, S. (2019). Organizational-Level Determinants Of Participation In Workplace Health Promotion Programs: A Cross-Company Study. *BMC Public Health*.
- [17] Lovett, N., & Lovett, T. (2016). Wellbeing In Education: Staff Matter. *International Journal Of Social Science And Humanity*.
- [18] Mayer, S. C. (2019). Wellbeing In The Workplace: A Comprehensive Model And Best-Practices From Top-Employers: Adaption Of PERMA(H).
- [19] Mazzetti, G., Biolcati, R., Guglielmi, D., Vallesi, C., & Schaufeli, W. B. (2016). Individual Characteristics Influencing Physicians’ Perceptions Of Job Demands And Control: The Role Of Affectivity, Work Engagement And Workaholism. *International Journal Of Environmental Research And Public Health*.
- [20] Moog, R. C. (2021). The PERMA Well-Being Profile Of Graduate Students . In *DLSU Research Congress 2021 De La Salle University, Manila, Philippines*.
- [21] Okello, D. R., & Gilson, L. (2015). Exploring The Influence Of Trust Relationships On Motivation In The Health Sector: A Systematic Review. *Human Resources For Health*.
- [22] Orji, M. G., & Yakubu, G. N. (2020). Effective Stress Management And Employee Productivity In The Nigerian Public Institutions; A Study Of National Galary Of Arts, Abuja, Nigeria. *Budapest International Research And Critics Institute-Journal (BIRCI-Journal)*.
- [23] Ortega, R. A., & Cruz, R. A.-D. (2016). Ducators’ Attitude Towards Outcomes-Based Educational Approach In English Second Language Learning. *American Journal Of Educational Research*.
- [24] Osborne, S., & Hammoud, M. S. (2017). Effective Employee Engagement In The Workplace. *International Journal Of Applied Management And Technology*.
- [25] Pandey, K., Thurman, M., Johnson, S. D., Acharya, A., Johnston, M., Klug, E. A., Et Al. (2021). Mental Health Issues During And After COVID-19 Vaccine Era. *Brain Research Bulletin*.
- [26] Peña-Sarrionandia, A., Mikolajczak, M., & Gross, J. J. (2015). Integrating Emotion Regulation And Emotional Intelligence Traditions: A Meta-Analysis. *Frontiers In Psychology*.
- [27] Pilcher, J. J., & Morris, D. M. (2020). Sleep And Organizational Behavior: Implications For Workplace Productivity And Safety. *Frontiers In Psychology*.
- [28] Pilgrim, K., & Bohnet-Joschko, S. (2019). Selling Health And Happiness How Influencers Communicate On Instagram About Dieting And Exercise: Mixed Methods Research. *BMC Public Health*.
- [29] Portoghese, I., Galletta, M., Coppola, R. C., Finco, G., & Campagna, M. (2014). Burnout And Workload Among Health Care Workers: The Moderating Role Of Job Control. *Safety And Health At Work*.
- [30] Pravamayee, S. (2014). Strategy To Develop An Effective Workplace Environment. *International Journal Of Language & Linguistics*.

- [31] Putri, E. M., Ekowati, V. M., Supriyanto, A. S., & Mukaffi, Z. (2019). The Effect Of Work Environment On Employee Performance Through Work Discipline. *International Journal Of Research - GRANTHAALAYAH*, 7(4), 132-140.
- [32] Rinne, J., Koskinen, S., Leino-Kilpi, H., Saaranen, T., & Salminen, L. (2021). Self-Conductive Interventions By Educators Aiming To Promote Individual Occupational Well-Being—A Systematic Review. *International Journal Of Educational Research*.
- [33] Rosales, R. M. (2015). Energizing Social Interactions At Work: An Exploration Of Relationships That Generate Employee And Organizational Thriving.
- [34] Sabando, C. M., & Alo, E. B. (2021). The Quality And Utilization Of School Health Services Of A State University In The Philippines. *Philippine Social Science Journal*.
- [35] Sandler, K. (2023). Analysis Of Factors That Predict Positive Emotion And Well-Being Using Continuous Tracking. *Virginia Journal Of Business, Technology, And Science*.
- [36] Schaufeli, W. B. (2017). Applying The Job Demands-Resources Model: A ‘How To’ Guide To Measuring And Tackling Work. *Organizational Dynamics*.
- [37] Scheepers, R. A., Boerebach, B. C., Arah, O. A., Heineman, M. J., & Lombarts, K. M. (2015). A Systematic Review Of The Impact Of Physicians’ Occupational Well-Being On The Quality Of Patient Care. *International Journal Of Behavioral Medicine*.
- [38] Sinclair, R. R., Probst, T. M., Watson, G. P., & Bazzoli, A. (2021). Caught Between Scylla And Charybdis: How Economic Stressors And Occupational Risk Factors Influence Workers’ Occupational Health Reactions To COVID-19. *Applied Psychology*.
- [39] Stoewen, D. L. (2016). Wellness At Work: Building Healthy Workplaces. *The Canadian Veterinary Journal*, , 57(11), 1188.
- [40] Strange, K. E., Troutman-Jordan, M., & Mixer, S. J. (2023). Influence Of Spiritual Engagement On Appalachian Older Adults’ Health. *Journal Of Psychosocial Nursing And Mental Health Services*.
- [41] Strout, K., Fayeza Ahmed, K. S., Howard, E. P., Sassatelli, E., & Mcfadden, K. (2018). What Are Older Adults Wellness Priorities? A Qualitative Analysis Of Priorities Within Multiple Domains Of Wellness. *Healthy Aging Research*.
- [42] WHO. (N.D.). WHO Healthy Workplace Framework And Model. Geneva, Switzerland: World Health Organisation.